

Additional File 8. Fluorescence Activated Cell Sorting (FACS) analysis of bone marrow extracts. Green fluorescence analysis of cells harvested from the femurs and tibias of **(a)** a control mouse that received no cells **(b)** a mouse that received mMSCs IC display no evidence of ZsGreen⁺ cells in the bone marrow.